

Application of Dynamic Vibration Absorber in Noise Control of whole Vehicle

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Abstract. As cars become quieter the sound quality of components becomes more critical in the customer perception of car quality. Considering that middle frequency noise plays an important roll for internal noise, the noise signals in the range from 200Hz to 500Hz are specially emphasized. Then the acoustic evaluation parameters, such as Sound Pressure Level, Acceleration have been evaluated. Judged from experiences and measuring results, an abnormal noise comes from engine mounts, through the use of dynamic vibration absorber on engine mounts, Vibration on engine mounts and Sound Pressure Level in interior vehicle were greatly improved. At the same time, subjective evaluation also indicated that there was no complaint any more in passenger compartment. Dynamic vibration absorber can properly solve the abnormal noise.

Introduction

As car manufacturers design quieter cars to reduce power train noise, road and wind noise, the sound quality of systems with electric motors becomes more and more important for improving customer perception of overall vehicle quality [1]. Electric motors are normally used in cars for applications such as generators, power windows, windshield wipers, seat adjustment, etc, [2]. Engine Mounts is a very important part which can the transfer structure-borne noise from motor to car body, when it is well designed, the vibration and sound in passenger compartment will be greatly reduced. The increased requirements of sound quality from customers will force the car manufacturer to focus on the noise level of whole vehicle, including component noise.

The human beings are very sensitive for the linearity of sounds, when the sounds are smoothly changed with engine speed, things will better. In the analysis of the experiment data special attention was paid to the influence of the nonlinearity of sound. During the development process of one new vehicle, it is complained that there is an abrupt high level noise in acceleration, especially when the engine speed is more than 4000 rpm, it sounds like metal click, which causes huge unpleasant feeling. Therefore, the experimental results were analyzed to yield information about which of the characters that were perceptually most prominent, and finally we used the dynamic vibration absorber to reduce the complaints.

Method

Measurement of Noise Source. The measurement of the complained vehicle was made in a semi-anechoic room at Shanghai Volkswagen Corporation, using Artemis System and two Microphones placed on engine bay and driver seat. The Microphone on driver seat was adjusted in ear position for an average male driver. Due to the complained noise comes out from engine bay, another Microphone was chose to be set in the engine bay. Measurements of the sound were made with 3rd Gear from 1000 rpm to 6000 rpm. The frequency characteristics of the test sounds are

presented in Fig.1. The abnormal frequencies were around 500Hz. The acceleration on engine mounts was also recorded, which showed that the abnormal noise was probably from engine mounts.

Fig. 1 Campbell of abnormal sound at driver's ear

Identification of Noise Source. Since the abnormal noise emitted probably from engine or its auxiliary, the next step is to identify the location of this abnormal noise source. According to the analysis results, the abnormal noise is about 500 Hz and is one kind of structure-borne noise. Therefore, except the microphone in engine bay, another accelerometer was placed on the engine mounts. The detailed positions of Accelerometer is presented in Fig.2. The sound pressure levels at driver's ear and the acceleration on engine mounts are displayed as the function of engine speed in Fig.3.

Fig. 2 vibration measuring point in engine bay

The results show that the noise at driver's ear is engine speed varying signal, and there is a strong correlation between SPL at driver's ear and Vibration on engine mounts when the filter of 1/3-octave band 500Hz was used. To conclude, the abnormal high frequency noise maybe comes from engine mounts, therefore, a dynamic vibration absorber (DVA) with resonance frequency of 500Hz could be equipped on the engine mounts. The detailed position of dynamic vibration absorber is presented in Fig.4.

Fig. 4 the position of dynamic vibration absorber on engine mounts

Results and Discussion

In order to check the effect of the dynamic vibration absorber, the measurement was made also in semi-anechoic room; the measuring points were the same as before. The results show that the SPL at driver's ear was obviously reduced by about 5dB at 4500rpm, and the peak of vibration on engine mounts at 4500rpm was also greatly reduced, which is presented in Fig.5. To conclude, dynamic vibration absorber with proper resonance frequency is an effective measure for the reduction of structure-borne noise in vehicle.

For the noise control in whole vehicle, there are always several ways to do, one is the control of transfer path, which is frequently used to solve the noise problem; the other is the control of noise source, which is always effective. Dynamic vibration absorber is one of the frequently used methods to control the source of noise.

Fig. 5(a) noise level at driver's ear

(b) vibration on engine mounts

Summary

Sound pressure level of 1/3 Octave band 500Hz showed a strong correlation with subjective evaluations for engine mounts noise, which leads to a bad perception of sound quality. The most important thing for noise control in whole vehicle is to identify the source and then to minimize its noise emission. Good sound quality was considered to be of high quality, which should be smooth and linear by acceleration or deceleration.

From the results of this study the following recommendations can be made: focus should be on the source of noise, DVA is a possible measure to solve the structure-borne noise. If the proper resonance frequency of DVA is chosen, good reduction of noise level could be got.

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